

In the initial stages of infestation, the central leaves of the plant dry up, like those of plants under stem borer attack. The beetle burrows into the base of the rice plant and cuts the stem from the ground level below the soil surface. After feeding on one plant, the beetle feeds on another from the same hill thus

killing the entire hill. A maximum of 5 beetles per hill (av 2) were observed.

The beetles cause patchy damage in the field. Their peak activity period is at night. Peak damage by this pest is observed in Jan-Jul when the crop is in the vegetative growth stage.

This pest attacks rice seedlings in the

nursery stage and also the irrigated crops in flooded fields. Severe infestation by black beetles is sporadic and normally restricted to small areas. Only rice is attacked by this insect pest while other kharif crops remain unmolested under natural infestation conditions. *ℒ*

Effect of *Leptocorisa* sp. on rice grain filling

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Leptocorisa sp. are common rice bugs in the low country wet zone of Sri Lanka. Nymphs and adults damage rice from flowering through dry dough stage.

We recorded damage caused by *Leptocorisa* sp. in observational trials with BW267-3 and Bg 94-1. Agronomic practices were common to all treatments. Complete insect control was used from seeding to flowering.

At early flowering, 12 panicles were randomly selected. Six were placed individually in plastic cages with 10 *Leptocorisa* nymphs/cage, and 6 were caged without insects. Cages were checked daily and insect density was maintained until harvest. Grain discoloration, percent unfilled grains, and grain weight were recorded. Grain weight was determined by weighing the

whole panicle, which included filled, partially filled, and unfilled grains.

Nymphs began feeding at flowering and adults fed until hard dough stage. Although puncture marks were not visible, milk exuded from some grains.

Level of grain discoloration was

similar in all treatments, indicating that the insects were not its cause.

Treatments with *Leptocorisa* had nearly 100% unfilled grains (see figure); insect-free treatments had 20% unfilled grains. Average 100-grain weight was 5.5 g with insects and 10 g without. *ℒ*

Controlling brown planthopper (BPH) with granular insecticides in India

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Summer rice (Jan-May) grown on irrigated coastal areas in Orissa is regularly attacked by BPH. In 1981-83, we evaluated 12 granular insecticides for controlling BPH at OUAT.

Three replications of insecticides were broadcast at 1.5 kg ai/ha at 45 d after transplanting in fields planted to

Field evaluation of 12 granular insecticides for controlling BPH, Bhubaneswar, India.^a

Insecticide	Adults + nymphs/10 has at 20-25 DAT			Grain yield (t/ha)		
	1981	1982	1983	1981	1982	1983
Control	40 cd	49 c	1090 e	1.9 a	3.6 a	1.4 a
Bendiocarb 4G	36 bcd	—	—	2.5 abc	—	—
BPMC 4G	21 a	12 a	80 b	3.3 de	4.3 bc	3.7 bcd
Carbofuran	24 ab	12 a	0 a	3.5 e	4.4 c	4.7 d
Carbosulfan	—	25 ab	102 bc	—	4.4 bc	4.2 cd
Carbaryl + lindane	—	—	935 e	—	—	1.5 a
chlorpyrifos	—	34 bc	763 e	—	4.3 bc	1.3 a
Diazinon	—	—	920 e	—	—	2.4 ab
Disulfoton	32 bcd	22 a	245 cd	2.4 ab	3.6 a	3.3 bcd
Ethoprophos	—	—	398 de	—	—	2.6 abc
Isoprocarb	27 abc	13 a	—	2.7 bcd	3.8 ab	—
Phorate	43 de	10 a	645 e	3.2 cde	4.0 abc	2.2 ab
Quinalphos	62 e	—	—	3.0 bcde	—	—

^aSeparation of means in a column by DMRT at the 5% level; — = not included in study, DAT = days after treatment.

susceptible Jaya. At 20-25 d after treatment, when BPH population peaked, adults and nymphs were counted on 10 randomly selected hills per treatment. BPH populations were larger in 1983 than in 1982.

Carbofuran, BPMC, and carbosulfan controlled BPH best (see table). *℥*

Mites attack IR56 in Vallanad, Tamil Nadu

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Rice mite *Oligonychus oryzae* (Hirst) attacked IR56 on the State Seed Farm in Vallanad in Sep 1985. The farm is irrigated for three seasons in a year. At 50 d after planting in a 6.5-ha block with 4 ha of IR50 and 2.5 ha of IR56, IR56 had 90-100% infestation and IR50 was mite-free.

IR56 had a mean population of 70 nymphs and adult mites/2 cm² leaf area and a mean of 96 eggs/cm² leaf area. Eggs, nymphs, and adults were on both leaf blade surfaces. Eggs were globular and pale white, nymphs were white, and adults were greyish white.

Mite feeding caused white spots on leaf surfaces, which later coalesced into white patches. Infested plants became yellowish white with severe leaf mottling.

Unusually high temperatures and dry weather (mean maximum temperature 35°C and minimum 30°C) for 30 d before the infestation may have encouraged high populations. *℥*

Rice gall midge (GM) in Tarai region of Uttar Pradesh

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The rice GM *Orseolia oryzae* is considered to be one of the major pests of rice. It has been reported in small pockets of Eastern Uttar Pradesh. In 1972, in the central and western Tarai region where rice is grown as a kharif crop, gall midge was reported from a very small area in Lakhimpur Kheri district. Since then, there was no report of its occurrence. While conducting a production oriented survey in 1984, we came across GM-infested fields in Mala

village and the Amaria block of Pilibhit district. Infestation was observed in the widely grown variety Jaya, which was then in the panicle initiation stage. There was 20-25% infestation in Mala, and 10-15% in the Amaria block.

Infested tillers were brought to the glasshouse to observe adult emergence. Only one female fly emerged and was identified as *Orseolia* sp. (presumably rice GM). Along with the adults, some parasites also emerged and were identified as *Propieroscytus mirificus* Girault (Pteromalidae). These may be larval, pupal, or larval-pupal parasites.

The infested fields were along the forest but areas one kilometer away from it showed no GM infestation. The same forest belt continues toward the western side, Pantnagar being about 40 km away from Mala village. The GM appears to spread toward the western side of Tarai along the forest at a slow rate. Although no widespread infestation has been reported in Tarai, the trend is alarming.

In Tarai region, the temperature goes down below 0°C during winter. The survival and perpetuation of GM during off season is worth investigating, particularly its behavior in biotype differential rice varieties. *℥*

Pest Control and Management WEEDS

Influence of different ecological situations on weed emergence in wetland rice

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Thirteen locations surveyed during the rabi season (Sep-Dec) of 1984 revealed the predominance of sedges in double-cropped wet rice fields in Trichur district. Eleven species of weeds

classified under five groups were identified as follows: *Echinochloa crus-galli* (grass); *Cyperus iria*, *C. difformis*, *Scirpus supinus*, and *Fimbristylis miliacea* (sedges); *Ludwigia octovalvis*,

Table 1. Effect of different ecological conditions on weed count.

Treatment	Weed count (no./m ²)										
	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	<i>Scirpus supinus</i>	<i>Cyperus iria</i>	<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	<i>Sphaeranthus indicus</i>	<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i>	<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i>	<i>Nymphaea nouchali</i>	<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	<i>Marsilea quadrifolia</i>
Transplanted rice	2.4 (1.4)	98.0 (9.6)	0.0 (0.6)	2.4 (1.4)	0.0 (0.6)	0.8 (0.9)	9.8 (2.9)	1.2 (1.1)	3.2 (1.5)	18.4 (4.0)	2.2 (1.4)
Wet sown rice	0.0 (0.6)	56.8 (7.2)	10.0 (3.2)	67.2 (7.6)	6.4 (2.3)	0.0 (0.6)	2.4 (1.4)	0.0 (0.6)	0.0 (0.6)	14.4 (3.7)	0.0 (0.6)
Wet fallow	2.4 (1.4)	267.2 (16.3)	6.4 (2.5)	10.6 (3.2)	0.0 (0.6)	0.0 (0.6)	6.6 (2.5)	4.2 (2.0)	1.6 (1.1)	8.8 (2.5)	1.2 (1.1)
Dry fallow	0.2 (0.7)	273.6 (16.4)	8.2 (2.9)	24.2 (4.8)	149.2 (11.7)	24.8 (4.9)	0.0 (0.6)	0.0 (0.6)	0.0 (0.6)	0.0 (0.6)	0.0 (0.6)
CD at 5%	ns	3.4	0.7	3.0	2.8	1.0	1.2	0.8	ns	2.3	0.7

^aFigures in parentheses are converted values.